

Supplementary Material: Toward Defeasible Machine Learning

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This document contains the full proofs that are summarised as proof sketches in the main paper. All notation, definitions, and theorem/lemma numbering follow the main paper.

1. Label Contradiction Mechanism

Lemma 1.1 (Label contradiction mechanism). *Let E be any set of implications whose antecedents are feature formulas and whose consequents are in $\{l, \neg l\}$. Let α be a body or feature pattern (hence satisfiable over the feature atoms). Then $E \models \neg\alpha$ if and only if $E \cup \{\alpha\} \models l$ and $E \cup \{\alpha\} \models \neg l$.*

Proof. $E \models \neg\alpha$ iff $E \cup \{\alpha\}$ is unsatisfiable. Since α is satisfiable over the feature atoms, the only source of unsatisfiability is the label atom l , which appears only in consequents, so unsatisfiability requires forcing both l and $\neg l$.

2. Proofs of the Depth Lemmas

Lemma 2.1 (Depth increase). *If $(B, \ell) \in \mathcal{R}$ and $(C, 1-\ell) \in \mathcal{R}$ with $C \subset B$, then $\text{depth}(B) \geq 1 + \text{depth}(C)$.*

Proof. Since $C \subset B$ and $(C, 1-\ell) \in \mathcal{R}$, we have $C \in \text{Opp}(B)$, so $\text{depth}(B) = 1 + \max\{\text{depth}(D) : D \in \text{Opp}(B)\} \geq 1 + \text{depth}(C)$.

Lemma 2.2 (Depth monotonicity). *If $B \subset D$ then $\text{depth}(B) \leq \text{depth}(D)$.*

Proof. Let $C \in \text{Opp}(B)$, so $(C, 1-\ell) \in \mathcal{R}$ and $C \subset B$. Since $B \subset D$, we get $C \subset D$, so $\text{Opp}(B) \subseteq \text{Opp}(D)$. If $\text{Opp}(B) = \emptyset$ the inequality holds trivially. Otherwise, $\text{depth}(D) = 1 + \max\{\text{depth}(C) : C \in \text{Opp}(D)\} \geq 1 + \max\{\text{depth}(C) : C \in \text{Opp}(B)\} = \text{depth}(B)$.

Lemma 2.3 (Maximal depth witness). *For every complete feature pattern F , there exists a most specific applicable rule $(B, \ell) \in \mathcal{M}(F)$ with $\text{depth}(B) = \text{depth}(F)$.*

Proof. Let $k = \text{depth}(F)$ and choose $(D, \ell) \in \mathcal{A}(F)$ with $\text{depth}(D) = k$. If $(D, \ell) \in \mathcal{M}(F)$ take $B = D$ and we are done. Otherwise some $(D_1, \ell_1) \in \mathcal{A}(F)$ has $D \subset D_1$. If $\ell_1 \neq \ell$ then the depth-increase lemma gives $\text{depth}(D_1) \geq k + 1$, contradicting maximality of k . So $\ell_1 = \ell$, and depth monotonicity gives $\text{depth}(D_1) \geq k$, hence $\text{depth}(D_1) = k$. Repeating and using finiteness gives termination at some $(B, \ell) \in \mathcal{M}(F)$ with $\text{depth}(B) = k$.

3. Full Proof of the Description of E_i

Lemma 3.1 (Description of E_i). *Assume \mathcal{R} satisfies strict global exception closure, sanity, and no total override. For every $i \geq 0$, $E_i = \{B \rightarrow \gamma : (B, \ell) \in \mathcal{R}, \gamma = l \text{ iff } \ell = 1, \text{depth}(B) \geq i\}$.*

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Proof. By induction on i . The base case $i = 0$ holds because E_0 is the full materialisation and $\text{depth}(B) \geq 0$ for every body.

Inductive step: assume the description holds for E_i . Fix $(B, \ell) \in \mathcal{R}$ with label consequent γ . We show $B \rightarrow \gamma \in E_{i+1}$ iff $\text{depth}(B) \geq i + 1$. *Forward.* Suppose $\text{depth}(B) \geq i + 1$. There exists $C \in \text{Opp}(B)$ with $\text{depth}(C) \geq i$, with opposite label consequent $\neg\gamma$. By the inductive hypothesis both $B \rightarrow \gamma$ and $C \rightarrow \neg\gamma$ are in E_i . Since $C \subset B$, any valuation satisfying B also satisfies C , so $E_i \cup \{B\}$ forces both γ and $\neg\gamma$. By the label contradiction mechanism, $E_i \models \neg B$, so $B \rightarrow \gamma \in E_{i+1}$.

Reverse. Suppose $\text{depth}(B) = i$. Let F be a witness completion for (B, ℓ) (exists by no total override), and let u match F on feature atoms and satisfy γ . We show u satisfies every implication in E_i . Take $D \rightarrow \delta \in E_i$ with $u \models D$. Then $F \models D$, so D and B are compatible. If $\delta = \gamma$ then $u \models D \rightarrow \delta$. If $\delta = \neg\gamma$ then $(D, 1-\ell) \in \mathcal{R}$ is compatible with B , so closure gives $D \subset B$ or $B \subset D$. If $D \subset B$ then $\text{depth}(D) \leq i - 1$, contradicting membership in E_i . If $B \subset D$ then $F \models D$, contradicting the witness property. So $\delta = \neg\gamma$ is impossible, u satisfies all of E_i , and $E_i \not\models \neg B$, giving $B \rightarrow \gamma \notin E_{i+1}$.

4. Full Proof of Proposition 4.6 (Depth = BaseRank)

Proposition 4.1. *Assume \mathcal{R} satisfies strict global exception closure, sanity, and no total override, and let $\mathcal{K} := \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{R})$. For every rule body B and every complete feature pattern F , $\text{depth}(B) = \text{br}_{\mathcal{K}}(B)$ and $\text{depth}(F) = \text{br}_{\mathcal{K}}(F)$.*

Proof. Rule bodies. By the description of E_i , $E_i \models \neg B$ iff $\text{depth}(B) \geq i + 1$, so the smallest i with $E_i \not\models \neg B$ is $i = \text{depth}(B)$, giving $\text{br}_{\mathcal{K}}(B) = \text{depth}(B)$.

Complete patterns. If $A(F) = \emptyset$ then $E_0 \cup \{F\}$ is satisfiable and $\text{br}_{\mathcal{K}}(F) = 0 = \text{depth}(F)$. Otherwise let $k := \text{depth}(F)$.

Lower bound ($\text{br}_{\mathcal{K}}(F) \geq k$): for any $i < k$ there exists an applicable body B with $\text{depth}(B) \geq i + 1$, and a predecessor $C \in \text{Opp}(B)$ with $\text{depth}(C) \geq i$. Since $F \models B$ and $C \subset B$, also $F \models C$. Both $B \rightarrow \gamma$ and $C \rightarrow \neg\gamma$ are in E_i by the description of E_i , so $E_i \cup \{F\}$ forces both l and $\neg l$, giving $E_i \models \neg F$.

Upper bound ($\text{br}_{\mathcal{K}}(F) \leq k$): suppose for contradiction $E_k \models \neg F$. By the label contradiction mechanism there exist $B \rightarrow l$ and $C \rightarrow \neg l$ in E_k with $F \models B$ and $F \models C$. By the description of E_i , $\text{depth}(B) \geq k$ and $\text{depth}(C) \geq k$. Since k is the maximum depth of any applicable body, $\text{depth}(B) = \text{depth}(C) = k$. These rules have opposite labels and are compatible, so closure gives $C \subset B$ (wlog). Then the depth-increase lemma gives $\text{depth}(B) \geq k + 1$, a contradiction. Hence $\text{br}_{\mathcal{K}}(F) = k$.

5. Full Proof of Lemma A.3 (Depth Partition = Tolerance Partition)

Lemma 5.1. *Assume \mathcal{R} satisfies strict global exception closure, sanity, and no total override. Let $D_i := \{B \sim \gamma \in \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{R}) : \text{depth}(B) = i\}$ and $p := \max\{\text{depth}(B) : (B, \ell) \in \mathcal{R}\}$. Then the ordered tolerance partition of $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{R})$ is (D_0, D_1, \dots, D_p) .*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{K}_{\geq i} := D_i \cup \dots \cup D_p$. We show that within $\mathcal{K}_{\geq i}$, exactly the conditionals in D_i are tolerated.

Every conditional in D_i is tolerated. Fix $B \sim \gamma \in D_i$. Let F be a witness completion and u the world matching F on features and satisfying γ . Then $u \models B \wedge \gamma$, so u verifies $B \sim \gamma$. For any $D \sim \delta \in \mathcal{K}_{\geq i}$ with $u \models D$: D and B are compatible. If $\delta = \gamma$ then u does not falsify $D \sim \delta$. If $\delta = \neg\gamma$ then closure gives $D \subset B$ or $B \subset D$. If $D \subset B$ then $\text{depth}(D) \leq i - 1$, contradicting membership in $\mathcal{K}_{\geq i}$. If $B \subset D$ then $F \models D$, contradicting the witness property. So u falsifies nothing in $\mathcal{K}_{\geq i}$.

No conditional in D_d with $d > i$ is tolerated. Fix $B \sim \gamma \in D_d$. Since $\text{depth}(B) = d > 0$ there exists $C \in \text{Opp}(B)$ with $\text{depth}(C) = d - 1 \geq i$. Any world u verifying $B \sim \gamma$ satisfies B , hence also C (since $C \subset B$). Then u falsifies $C \sim \neg\gamma \in \mathcal{K}_{\geq i}$, so $B \sim \gamma$ is not tolerated.

Combining: within $\mathcal{K}_{\geq i}$ exactly D_i is tolerated, so $\text{OP}(\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{R})) = (D_0, D_1, \dots, D_p)$.